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MEN AND HYPERANDROGENIA

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Annotation. *The term “hyperandrogenism” refers to excessive synthesis of androgenic hormones [1]. Although this condition can develop in both sexes, the concept is currently used primarily in relation to women. Today, the problem of hyperandrogenism in women is a widely studied and discussed issue, addressed at every reproductive health conference, while in relation to men this issue is practically not addressed. If we consider hyperandrogenism as an independent nosological unit, then we can conditionally distinguish physiological hyperandrogenism - caused by overproduction of testosterone and/or dihydrotestosterone (DHT) with normal levels of luteinizing hormone (LH) and pathological - accompanied by suppression of LH caused by serious concomitant somatic pathology of the adrenal glands, testicles or taking drugs with an androgenic effect, anabolic steroids [2]. A separate type of hyperandrogenism is an increase in androgens in men with androgen-producing tumors of the testicles or adrenal glands [3, 4]. Our study characterized variants of physiological hyperandrogenism in men.*

Keywords: *androgens, LH, DHT, testosterone, acne*

МУЖЧИНЫ И ГИПЕРАНДРОГЕНИЯ

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Аннотация. Термин «гиперандрогения» относится к избыточному синтезу андрогенных гормонов [1]. Хотя это состояние может развиваться у представителей обоих полов, в настоящее время это понятие используется преимущественно по отношению к женщинам. Сегодня проблема гиперандрогении у женщин является широко изучаемой и обсуждаемой проблемой, рассматриваемой на каждой конференции по репродуктивному здоровью, в то время как в отношении мужчин этот вопрос практически не рассматривается. Если рассматривать гиперандрогению как самостоятельную нозологическую единицу, то условно можно выделить гиперандрогению физиологическую - вызванную гиперпродукцией тестостерона и/или дигидротестостерона (ДГТ) при нормальном уровне лютеинизирующего гормона (ЛГ) и патологическую - сопровождающуюся подавлением ЛГ, вызванную тяжелыми заболеваниями. сопутствующая соматическая патология надпочечников, яичек или прием препаратов с андрогенным действием, анаболических стероидов [2]. Отдельным видом гиперандрогении является повышение уровня андрогенов у мужчин с андрогенпродуцирующими опухолями яичек или надпочечников [3, 4]. В нашем исследовании охарактеризованы варианты физиологической гиперандрогении у мужчин.

Ключевые слова: андрогены, ЛГ, ДГТ, тестостерон, акне.

Purpose of the study. To characterize the variants of physiological hyperandrogenism in men.

Materials and methods. Place and time of the study. Samarkand branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Endocrinology. The study was carried out between September 2021 and January 2023.

Populations studied. The formation of groups was carried out from patients who sought medical help at the SFRSNPTSE. Inclusion criteria were male gender; age over 18 years; elevated levels of total testosterone and/or DHT; normal LH level. Non-inclusion criteria were neoplasms of the hypothalamic-pituitary region, testicles, and adrenal glands; congenital dysfunction of the adrenal cortex; use of any drugs from the groups of antiestrogens, estrogens, gestagens, aromatase inhibitors, antiandrogens, gonadotropins, anabolic steroids, steroidogenesis inhibitors; alcoholism/drug addiction; diabetes mellitus types 1 and 2; hypercortisolism syndrome. Exclusion criteria were not provided. A total of 100 patients were included in the study, age 26 (minimum 18; maximum 58) years.

Method of forming a sample from the population being studied. The sample was formed using a continuous method.

Study design. A continuous, cross-sectional study of men with elevated levels of total testosterone and/or DHT.

Methods. During the study, the volume and structure of the prostate, the volume of the testicles were assessed using ultrasound using the Aplio 500 device No. 416508; the levels of LH (norm 2.5–11.0 U/l), total testosterone (norm 12.0–30.0 nmol/l), sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) (norm 12–65 nmol/l) were determined; DHT (norm 250–990 pg/ml) on a Vitros ECi automatic analyzer (Johnson and Johnson (UK)) using the enhanced chemiluminescence method. The level of free testosterone was determined by the calculation method according to Vermeullen (norm 243–900 pmol/l) [5]. Analysis of the hormonal status of patients with hyperandrogenism made it possible to form 4 groups of patients based on laboratory characteristics.

1. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone and SHBG (n=12).
2. Patients with elevated total testosterone levels and normal SHBG levels (n=15).

3. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone, DHT with normal levels of SHBG (n=11).

4. Patients with elevated DHT levels with normal levels of total testosterone and SHBG (n=62).

Statistical analysis. Principles for calculating sample size Pilot study. The sample size was not previously calculated.

Methods of statistical data analysis. The obtained data were processed using the statistical software package STATISTICA 13.0 (StatSoft

Inc., USA) [6]. Differences between groups were determined using the Mann–Whitney U test for quantitative characteristics and Fisher's exact test for qualitative ones. Differences between groups were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. When comparing the groups, statistically significant differences were revealed in a number of indicators. The first group of patients was statistically significantly different from the other groups of patients in that they were older; these patients were also characterized by the presence of excess mass. The prostate volume of men in this group was statistically significantly higher than that of men in other groups. In addition, for this group of patients, despite the high level of total testosterone (the level of free testosterone was statistically significantly lower compared to that in patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups, but higher than in men of the 4th group), there was no Acne complaints are typical. Alopecia was also rare. On the contrary, patients of group 2 complained of acne, but the prevalence of this symptom even in this group was statistically significantly lower than in patients of group 3. At the same time, the incidence of alopecia was significantly lower than in patients of both groups 3 and 4. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone and DHT (group 3) had the most striking clinical manifestations of hyperandrogenism. All patients from this group complained of acne, as well as increased hair loss on the head. Alopecia was also typical for patients in group 4. Complaints about the presence of acne were present, but their frequency differed statistically significantly compared to group 1, increasing, and compared to other groups, decreasing. Men in group 4 were characterized by statistically significantly lower levels of free testosterone compared to patients in other groups.

Discussion Representativeness of samples. It is not possible to assess the representativeness of the sample in relation to the general population, since the selection of the sample was carried out using a continuous method from patients observed only in the federal research center.

Comparison with other publications. In clinical practice, hyperandrogenism can cause the development of a number of diseases [7]. Increased levels of testosterone, DHT, or genetically determined sensitivity of androgen receptors can lead to the development of a disease such as androgenetic

alopecia [8]. In our study, it was identified in men with elevated DHT levels, regardless of testosterone levels, which is consistent with the modern concept of the influence of elevated DHT levels on the development of androgenetic alopecia [9]. Thus, in a study by H. Schweikert et al. It has been demonstrated that hair follicles and scalp of patients with androgenetic alopecia contain higher concentrations of DHT than healthy tissue samples [10]. When determining the concentration of DHT and testosterone in 52 patients of both sexes with early androgenetic alopecia, no statistically significant increase was found, but the authors found a significant increase in the DHT/testosterone ratio [11]. Another disease in the development of which hyperandrogenism can be of great importance is acne [12]. Under the influence of androgens, the volume of sebum increases, in which the concentration of essential alpha-linolenic acid, the main regulator of keratinocyte differentiation of the pilosebaceous follicle duct, decreases, which is manifested by the appearance of open and closed comedones and creates favorable conditions for the proliferation of microflora [13]. According to the results of the study, acne was typical for men with increased levels of total and free testosterone, while the presence of increased levels of DHT led to an increase in the prevalence of acne, up to 100% of cases. However, this situation did not apply to men from group 1, since their increased level of total testosterone, strictly speaking, was not a sign of hyperandrogenism, but was due to an increase in SHBG levels. At the same time, the level of free testosterone, which reflects the degree of androgen saturation of the body, was statistically significantly lower than that observed in groups 2 and 3. Although the level of this indicator was statistically significantly higher than that in the 4th group, the values of the level of free testosterone obtained in men of both the 1st and 4th groups were within the reference values. An increase in SHBG levels is typical for men in the older age group, while in older men it more often leads to the development of testosterone deficiency [14]. If in patients with age the secretion of total testosterone is not impaired, then an increase in SHBG does not lead to a deficiency of free testosterone - it remains within the reference values. A characteristic feature of patients in group 1 was also an increase in the volume of the prostate gland, which may be explained by the age of the patients. Researchers have demonstrated an association between a man's age and the development of benign prostatic hyperplasia [15]. In the young patients included in our study, despite elevated androgen levels, no changes in prostate volume or structure were detected.

Clinical significance of the results. The results obtained are important for clinical practice, since they allow differential diagnosis of various types of hyperandrogenism, which is necessary for personalized treatment. The detection of increased levels of total testosterone during examination of elderly men necessitates the assessment of the SHBG level with further calculation of the level of free testosterone, which, when obtaining values of this indicator that fit into the reference interval, will eliminate hyperandrogenism in the patient.

Limitations of the study. The limitations of the study are problems with the representativeness of the sample in relation to the general population (formed only from patients of a large federal center), as well as the use in the study of a calculation method rather than a direct method for determining free testosterone.

Directions for further research. In continuation of the study, it is planned to study risk factors characteristic of different types of hyperandrogenism associated with steroidogenesis.

Conclusion. Increased androgen levels can be detected at any age. Moreover, in men of the older age group, an increase in the level of total testosterone may not indicate hyperandrogenism, but be caused by an increase in the secretion of SHBG and not be accompanied by an increase in the level of free testosterone. In young patients, clinical manifestations hyperandrogenism depends on its variant. Thus, patients with elevated levels of DHT were characterized by androgenetic alopecia. Acne was common in men with elevated levels of total and free testosterone, although elevated DHT also exacerbated the problem.

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